

Empowerment of Communities in Indonesia's Border Region through Raising Awareness of State Defense to Support National Defense

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ABSTRACT: Indonesia as the largest archipelagic country in the world with a coastline of 108,000 kilometers, has land borders with three neighboring countries and Indonesian waters borders with ten neighboring countries, so it is the obligation of the Indonesian government and all citizens to maintain the integrity of its territory. In maintaining the integrity of its territory directly adjacent to other countries, based on geographical conditions in terms of this approach, the border area should be placed as the front fence in the national defense system.

This research was conducted to determine the condition of the people of Indonesia's border areas and aims to analyze the efforts in empowering the people of the border areas through increasing awareness of defending the country. By using a qualitative descriptive method, the data to be taken comes from books, previous research, scientific articles, literature and news from the official website. Along with global developments, the forms of threats that exist are not only physical threats but also non-physical threats. With Indonesia's geographical conditions, it will certainly have a big influence on the people in the region and will pose various threats if not managed properly, lack of synergy between the central government and local governments in managing border areas so that each sector or agency runs on its own. which resulted in the condition of the border area being left behind compared to its parent region, the low level of welfare and lack of attention from the government which resulted in the people living in the region preferring to interact with their neighboring countries, because all their necessities of life were available in their neighboring countries and were easily accessible, the low quality and The quantity of human resources results in a low awareness of defending the country and a lack of concern for environmental development, if these conditions are not immediately addressed by all of us and if ignored by all of us. can cause a very serious problem in the future. In response to this, it is necessary to make improvements, reorganization and strategic planning, including a complex arrangement for the empowerment of defense and security in the region so as to be able to maintain and detect and anticipate any vulnerabilities or threats that will arise. the strong one.

KEYWORDS -Community empowerment, Indonesian Border Area, Defend the Country, National Defense

I. INTRODUCTION

State defense is essentially all efforts carried out with the aim of defending the sovereignty of the state, the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from threats and disturbances to the integrity of the nation and state. To defend the country's sovereignty from threats and disturbances, Indonesia implements a universal people's defense and security system (sishankamrata) also known as a total defense system involving all national resources which are prepared in advance by the government. Implemented in a total, integrated, directed, and sustainable manner in order to uphold the

sovereignty of the state, maintain territorial integrity, and the safety of the entire nation from all forms of threats (Law Number 3 of 2002: article 1 paragraph 1 & 2). Indonesia is the largest archipelagic country in the world with a coastline of 108,000 kilometers (Pushidrosal, 2018), is the second longest country after Canada which has territorial boundaries with three neighboring countries, namely Malaysia, Papua New Guinea and Timor Leste. Then at sea, Indonesian waters are bordered by ten neighboring countries, namely: India, Singapore, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, the Philippines, Palau, Australia, Timor Leste and Papua New Guinea, so it is the obligation of the Indonesian government and all citizens to maintain the integrity of its territory. In maintaining the integrity of its territory directly adjacent to other countries, based on geographical conditions in terms of this approach, the border area should be placed as the front fence in the national defense system. The Frontier Region is as the leading foothold in projecting defense power. The meaning as a leading step, that the border does not only function as the physical boundary of the sovereign territory (Boundary of Sovereignty) in the context of the boundary or serves as a basic point of withdrawal (Base Point) the boundary of the national jurisdiction (LawNumber 43 of 2008).

The Coordinating Minister for Political, Legal and Security Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Wiranto said that defense and security in Indonesia's border areas are currently still fragile because they are not well maintained, there are no sources of life in the area, the lack of elementary schools, markets, health facilities, community craft centers that are able to create a new economy in border areas that make Indonesia's defense and security weak, this makes it easy for drugs, terrorists, illegal refugees, and other threats to enter (Ristiano, 2019).

The government of President JokoWidodo has issued Presidential Instruction Number 1 of 2021 concerning the Acceleration of Economic Development in the State Border Areas in Aruk, Motaain, and Skouw as one of the efforts to overcome lagging development in border areas. However, the Empowerment of Defense Areas, especially for people living in border areas, is felt to have not been implemented optimally by both the central and regional governments, this is none other than due to the fact that the regulations are not yet optimally implemented and an institution that regulates the empowerment of defense areas is not yet optimal. Human resources in the area indirectly, the resilience to defend the country is almost untouched due to the lack of a sense of one homeland and one nation that can be used as glue.

In order for community empowerment in border areas to be more optimal in facing the above threats, in supporting national defense it can be realized through fostering the potential of the local community which is carried out in an appropriate, directed, organized and integrated manner. The development of this potential is mainly directed at border communities to realize reserve components that are prepared early based on applicable regulations, so that they have the carrying capacity and deterrence capacity on land and at sea. In a state of peace, among others, it can be an eye and ear in supporting national defense, while in a state of war it can function as a supporting force for land and sea dimensions so that the national defense system can be realized.

II. METHOD

In preparing this research, the writer uses descriptive analysis method. The aim is to produce research reports that provide comprehensive and analytical explanations. Discussion and research results are in the form of critical studies or analysis. Then for the approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. The data collection technique used in this research is data collection through literature studies or library research which the authors get through books, scientific works, journals that are relevant to the topic of this paper, namely the empowerment of border area communities, and increasing awareness of defending the country. Library research is a technique of collecting data through various reading references that are considered relevant to the problem to be studied, then from the reading material a detailed understanding is carried out so as to obtain research findings. In the preparation of this paper, the author conducted an in-depth literature study to support the collection of research data that he felt would be necessary.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The ideals and national goals of the Indonesian people are stated in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution, namely the existence of an independent, united, sovereign, just and prosperous life. The

Indonesian government was formed to protect the entire Indonesian nation and the entire homeland of Indonesia and to promote public welfare, educate the nation's life and participate in carrying out world order based on independence, eternal peace and social justice.

Geographically, the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia consists of large and small islands scattered from Sabang and Merauke which is a gift to be grateful for, however, in increasing National Resilience in order to face vulnerabilities in border areas with neighboring countries, the government needs serious attention, so that must be maintained and managed as much as possible for the interests and prosperity of the Indonesian nation. The existence of people in border areas poses serious obstacles in carrying out the development, because the location is on the outskirts or separated from the main island, so it has not been fully touched by access to regular sea and air transportation. The guidance that has been carried out so far is still not optimal due to limited infrastructure and transportation advice, people in border areas of low quality and lack of attention from the central government and local governments as well as limited budget resources.

Various turbulences and multidimensional crises that have hit the Indonesian nation have created various social inequalities, among others, the uneven distribution of development implementation which has resulted in growth gaps between regions.

The history of the nation's struggle states that the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, which was proclaimed on August 17, 1945, is an archipelagic state. This implies that the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia is an inseparable unit, covering the land, sea and air areas above it. With such a large area, plus Indonesia's strategic position between two continents and two oceans, the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia can be used as an arena for unilateral interests for other countries.

The boundaries of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia are a legacy of the Dutch colonial era that has colonized the Indonesian people for hundreds of years. The policies of the Indonesian government in the old and new orders have placed the paradigm that the border area of the Indonesian state is not the front page, so that the border conditions become very vulnerable from illegal economic activities, ideological infiltration, socio-culture from other countries. This government policy has resulted in the low level of welfare of the people in the border areas, thereby reducing the resilience against various threats and disturbances.

Archipelago insight as a visional foundation is the basis for governance and development of the Indonesian nation which is inspired by national ideals and the environment, so as to produce a perspective or insight that gives a pattern to the mindset, attitude pattern, and pattern of action, the basic conception of Nusantara insight outlines the ground Indonesian water and its contents as a unified container and means of struggle for the life of the nation in a round and intact manner. Referring to the basic concept, the State of Indonesia is an archipelagic country which is a single unit, exploitation of natural resources used for the welfare of all people in a fair and equitable manner can be an adhesive factor for national unity.

As a geopolitical, Indonesia views aspects of the territory of the country and the natural resources contained therein as a political unit, an economic, social, cultural and security unit as a unified whole in the conduct of the Indonesian nation. The Archipelago Insight is a guideline for the implementation of social life, as a nation and greatly determines the achievement of national goals, strengthens the taste, attitude of the nation and country, a common determination that prioritizes the national interest to achieve national goals, in order to realize a unified national defense.

3.1 Efforts to support National Defense

In facing the development of a dynamic global strategic and defense environment, Indonesia has a concept of national defense, namely a universal defense system, which involves all levels of the people in an effort to maintain security. The conception of national defense becomes a guide for every citizen to be able to understand it as a form of; achievement of national goals; national interest; the nature of national defense; national defense system; national defense function; and the use of national defense components(Yusgiantoro:2014).

In Presidential Regulation Number 8 of 2021 concerning the General Policy of State Defense for 2020 - 2024, it is stated that the policy of developing a non-military defense posture is directed at capacity building, implemented through improving the quality of human resources and facilities and infrastructure of ministries,

institutions, and local governments by utilizing technological developments. Capacity building is directed at realizing:

1. Early vigilance, awareness of state defense, diplomatic ability, mastery of science and technology, economic and social resilience, moral strengthening, and other capabilities to support the implementation of national defense.
2. Public awareness and participation as the nation's strength in supporting national defense.
3. Deterrence and resilience of the nation in the face of every threat and dynamics of environmental change.

So that the role of the border area community through increasing awareness of state defense needs to be empowered so that it has implications for national defense.

3.2 The role of the border area community through increasing awareness of defending the state

In the Law of the Republic of Indonesia number 23 of 2019 concerning the management of national resources for National Defense, it is explained that State Defense is the determination, attitude, and behavior and actions of citizens in maintaining state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and the safety of the nation and state which is imbued with love. to the State based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution in ensuring the survival of the nation and state from various threats.

In accordance with the 1945 Constitution Article 30 Paragraph 1, which stipulates that every citizen has the right and is obliged to participate in the defense and security of the State, here it is necessary to involve all citizens, in this case the people of the border area, which is built through the cultivation of awareness of defending the state in the defense system. state, in essence, is to pay attention to the geographical position of Indonesia as an archipelagic country which brings several consequences in the field of defense, namely:

1. The preparation and readiness of troops to anticipate the coming threat must be high.
2. Troop mobility must be high which allows troops to be deployed throughout the Indonesian archipelago in a short time. This means that there must be an integration of support systems for land, sea and air transportation.
3. Logistics routes must cover the entire Indonesian archipelago.
4. Communication, Command, Control and Intelligence must be integrated and cover the entire territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

In order for the country's defense to be implemented, it requires the support of all potential national powers. This readiness for support will not just happen without a comprehensive management system for state defense awareness. State defense is an activity that is born by every citizen as the fulfillment of rights and obligations in the context of implementing national defense. Quoting Muhammad Azhar (2001), defending the country is like defending the homeland (geographical), loving the homeland (psychological), state stability (security) and loyalty to the nation and state (dedicative). Increasing awareness of defending the country by providing understanding, understanding of defending the country so that it becomes part of people's lives. State defense is empowered as the provision of strength and capability to the community to be able to carry out state defense. People who have the ability to defend the state are aware of their rights and obligations in various activities as social beings and as citizens. Of course, this empowerment is balanced with exemplary moral attitudes and a sense of national pride. The cultural agenda of defending the country is actually the agenda of the entire nation. Instilling the spirit of defending the country is a process of changing behavior in accordance with social institutions, so it is necessary to carry out continuous development.

3.3 Empowering Border Area Communities through Raising Awareness of State Defense to Support National Defense

Empowerment of the border area community is carried out by increasing understanding in the awareness of defending the State against the border area community through training, socialization, coaching and counseling about the knowledge of defending the State, the following efforts are taken:

1. The Ministry of Defense by involving state officials, political parties, scholars, national entrepreneurs, and public figures, in order to provide examples of the application of awareness of defending the state in

society, nation and state, carried out with full awareness. For this reason, a state defense awareness movement is needed which is carried out in stages and continues by forming cadres of state defense cadres throughout Indonesia starting in their respective organizational circles and in the community.

2. The Ministry of Defense together with the Ministry of Education perfects the National Defense education curriculum in schools or education from the elementary school to tertiary levels regarding the Citizenship Education curriculum and conducts studies involving Non-Governmental Organizations in order to examine more comprehensively the problem of implementing State defense education.

3. The Ministry of Defense and the Regional Government play a major role by involving community leaders, religious leaders, traditional leaders in fostering social, national and state harmony in the region, as a forum for national harmony to prevent the emergence of horizontal and vertical conflicts in the region. nuanced ethnicity, religion, race, and between groups.

4. The Ministry of Defense by involving the role of other State institutions that are directly or indirectly involved in the implementation of State defense education, the Ministry of Defense which carries out government functions must be directly involved or facilitate the formation and fostering of awareness of defending the State in accordance with the duties and scope of its authority.

5. The Ministry of Defense prepares educational facilities and infrastructure for State defense in the regions in accordance with the development of science and information technology, prepares and increases capable educators in the field of State defense so that the objectives are achieved.

6. The Ministry of Defense together with the central and regional governments establish a communication forum for awareness of State defense on a regular basis involving all components of the nation in order to increase awareness of defending the State, starting from the provincial level to the smallest level of government environment in the region.

7. The Ministry of Defense together with the central government in cooperation with the regional government in an integrated manner plan development in the border area or the outermost/frontier small islands that are few inhabited by building a large monument with the name of the local hero or a lighthouse as a sign that the territory or island belongs to Indonesia.

IV. CONCLUSION

Indonesia has 10 border areas with neighboring countries in the region, the boundaries of which have not yet been fully defined. Community empowerment in border areas is an effort to utilize various potentials that exist in border areas to support the development of border areas which are an integral part of national development as a manifestation of the government's political will which is carried out based on the potential of border areas as a real manifestation of the Archipelago Insight and in the context of implementing National Defense. in the border area.

From the discussion of the description of empowering the people of the border area through increasing awareness of defending the State, understanding nationalism and love for the homeland for national defense, it can be concluded that the border areas of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia are framed by state borders which have strategic value because the border area is a binder and affirmation. the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, functions as a means of state defense against all forms of threats and disturbances from abroad, either by land, by sea or by air. In this regard, the border area must have high capability and deterrence against all forms of threats, both military and non-military.

The factual condition of the border areas of the Republic of Indonesia is still far from what is expected, because most of the land border areas are forest with undulating topography to mountainous conditions so that it is very rarely inhabited by residents. The available artificial resources, facilities and infrastructure are still very limited, while the population is small with uneven distribution.

Development in border areas is still felt to be inadequate compared to the rapid development of development in neighboring bordering countries, people in border areas generally live below the poverty line and have low education, empowering human resources to be empowered optimally, it is necessary to have a concept of community development to improve quality and quantity, with the existence of appropriate and

consistent concepts based on the potential geographical conditions of each border area by involving the central government and local governments, relevant agencies, private parties or entrepreneurs and community leaders, so as to improve the standard of living, improve the quality of human resources and increasing awareness of defending the State, this is a tangible manifestation of increasing national defense in the region.

Geographical and demographic conditions that do not support the creation of dynamics in the life of the people of the border areas, both in the political, economic, socio-cultural and defense and security fields. In this regard, it is difficult for the people of the border areas to experience significant progress, from year to year there are not many changes. Such conditions cause border areas to have no deterrence, so they are very vulnerable to external military and non-military threats which result in weak National Defense.

To improve the ability of border area communities to have high deterrence against all threats and disturbances, it is necessary to build and foster through an inter-departmental and interdisciplinary approach with integrated funding and management involving multi-stakeholders, increasing attention and regulations of the central government on development, increasing awareness of defending the State, empowerment of land and sea defense areas as well as an increase in the quality of human resources in the region to support national defense.

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